

Methotrexate Induced Oral Mucositis in Rheumatoid Arthritis due to dosing error: Implication for Medication safety and Management

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Received on: 29 August 2024; Accepted on: 17 September 2024; Published on : 20 October 2024

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Abstract

Methotrexate prescriptions for a range of neoplastic conditions are widely known. A once-weekly low-dose regimen is recommended for the treatment of psoriasis and rheumatoid arthritis respectively. In addition to its medicinal benefits, it has a few side effects as well, such as mouth ulcers, which could be caused by overdosing on its once-weekly schedule. This case study details a patient who received methotrexate for rheumatoid arthritis and developed oral mucositis despite having intrinsic methotrexate toxicity.

The 59-year-old patient recently diagnosed with rheumatoid arthritis was receiving methotrexate therapy as a part of his treatment plan. The patient, however, unintentionally ingested an excessive dose of methotrexate because of a communication error that occurred during the medication administration process. She started displaying signs of oral mucositis, characterized by uncomfortable ulcers and oral mucosa inflammation, within a short period. The buccal mucosa, labial mucosa and tongue, of the patient's oral cavity displayed numerous ulcerative lesions upon examination. Due to the mucositis's severity, it was challenging to eat, speak, and perform regular oral hygiene procedures.

Keywords: Methotrexate, Rheumatoid Arthritis, Overdose, Toxicity

Introduction

Methotrexate (MTX) is an immunomodulatory drug acting as a folic acid antagonist, which is usually administered in high doses for treating leukemia, lymphomas, and tumors as a chemotherapy agent. Methotrexate irreversibly binds to the dihydrofolate reductase and thus reduces cell proliferative activity.¹ Moreover low dose of MTX is used in the treatment of some autoimmune disease such as rheumatoid arthritis, psoriasis, polymyositis, Systemic lupus erythematosus due to anti-inflammatory effects². Methotrexate has been used in the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis (RA) since the 1980s and to this day is often the first-line medication for rheumatoid arthritis treatment³. A dose of 5-35mg methotrexate is typically administered once per week. Toxicities to the bone marrow and digestive systems are the most frequent side effects of methotrexate therapy. Additionally, these side effects are dose dependent and potentially fatal; as a result, when they appear, methotrexate treatment is reduced or discontinued, and folic acid is given. Although stomatitis is a frequent side effect of methotrexate therapy when treating malignant disease, it is uncommon when using methotrexate therapy to treat rheu-

matoid arthritis⁴

In this report, a case of methotrexate-induced toxicity is presented, which posed a considerable diagnostic challenge due to the various medications the patient was receiving.

Case Report

A 59-year-old female presented to the Department of Oral Medicine and Radiology in 2022 with a chief complaint of painful oral ulcers and a burning sensation when consuming food for the past 2.5 months. The patient was apparently asymptomatic until 2 months prior when she noticed the development of multiple ulcers on the right and left buccal mucosa and labial mucosa. Initially small in size, gradually progressed to attain the varying size of 3cm×2cm in lower labial mucosa and 2cm×2cm in right buccal mucosa. The patient had a history of rheumatoid arthritis and Sjögren's syndrome (sicca syndrome) since 2017. Her medication regimen included: Methotrexate 15 mg once weekly, Folic acid 5 mg

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How to cite this article: Singh et al. : Methotrexate Induced Oral Mucositis in Rheumatoid Arthritis due to dosing error - Implication for Medication safety and Management. HTAJ OCD 2024

once weekly, Hydroxychloroquine (HCQ) 300 mg once daily, Pantoprazole once daily on an empty stomach, Prednisolone 2.5 mg every third day, Vitamin B12 injection intramuscularly once weekly, Carboxymethylcellulose eye drops thrice daily for both eyes

The clinical examination revealed erythematous areas with crustations and bleeding at the lips, sloughing in the lower labial vestibule, and an erythematous base covered with peeling mucosa and erosions. The mucositis was graded as Grade I. On palpation, the ulcers were tender, soft, friable, rough, shriveled in texture, and covered with slough, and were associated with bleeding.

A thorough review of the patient's outpatient card and a physical check of all medications indicated that the patient had mistakenly taken methotrexate daily instead of the prescribed weekly dosage since October 2022. The error was due to confusion between the brand names of methotrexate (Folitrax) and folic acid (Foltrate). Her initial laboratory blood testing showed early signs of bone marrow suppression (white blood count: 3100 cells/cumm, platelets: 230,000 cells/cumm) and elevated liver enzymes SGOT 84.42 U/L and total bilirubin 1.04mg/dl.

The clinical picture gave the impression was of oral mucositis secondary to methotrexate overdose. Treatment was initiated with discontinuation of methotrexate, oral rehydration solution powder, benzydamine hydrochloride mouthwash, glutathione 1 tab OD for three weeks, and triamcinolone 2 tab BD for 2 weeks. Over time, the patient's lesions healed with regression of all lesion.

Discussion

Methotrexate is used to treat a variety of malignancies, autoimmune disorders, and abortions. Active cellular uptake and active efflux transporters allow it into the cells. Once methotrexate enters the cell, it inhibits the enzyme dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR), which converts dihydrofolate (DHF) into tetrahydrofolate (THF). Thymidylate and purine synthesis are consequently reduced. When DNA synthesis stops, cells eventually lose the ability to proliferate.⁵ Because the medication is polyglutaminated, its intracellular presence is prolonged. As a result, cells, including lymphoblasts, synovial macrophages, and epithelia that are capable of effective polyglutamination, are more sensitive to this medication.⁶

The present case of methotrexate-induced oral mucositis in a patient with rheumatoid arthritis due to confusion between medication brand names is similar to the findings reported by Shrestha R, Ojha S K, Jha S, et al, where patients also developed mucositis due to inappropriate methotrexate dosing. The patient had misjudged the two medications and taken methotrexate 7.5 mg twice daily for the past five days and started developing symptoms, also the present case is similar to the finding of Verma M. 2018, where the patient took daily dose of methotrexate 7.5mg and developed grade IV mucositis. In Hosseini R, Brooks SP et al case report the patient with RA presented with worsening oral lesions over 2 weeks. She reported non-compliance with folic acid for 2 weeks while on MTX, Misadministration of the medication can lead to serious complications, and, importantly, even at low doses, methotrexate toxicity has the potential to be fatal. The fast cellular

turnover of these organs, where many cells are in the synthesis phase of the cell cycle and consequently particularly sensitive to the cytotoxic effects of methotrexate, may explain why relatively low doses of methotrexate can elicit both cutaneous and hematologic damage.⁷

Side effects of low-dose methotrexate are classified into the following three groups. The first group includes direct gastrointestinal and bone marrow toxicity. These side effects are dose-dependent, and the most common. The second group includes idiosyncratic or allergic reactions, and the third group is the long-term drug side effects, including cardiovascular and hepatic diseases, which are mainly caused by hyperhomocysteinemia. General side effects include gastrointestinal, leukocytopenia⁸, kidney failures, headache. Oral lesions are less common and occur mainly in the form of oral ulcers and mucositis in the case of folate deficiency.⁹

The differential diagnosis of oral ulcers is extensive and includes autoimmune diseases, recurrent aphthous stomatitis (RAS), viral and bacterial infections, agranulocytosis, allergic reactions, and drug side effects. Obtaining an accurate medical history and complete clinical examination can play a vital role in the precise diagnosis of the diseases.¹⁰

Conclusion

This case highlights the importance of clear patient education and accurate medication administration. The quick recognition and management of methotrexate induced oral mucositis led to successful recovery. It emphasizes the need for careful communication to prevent similar medication error.

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Fig. I

Fig. II

Fig I And 2 - Erythematous area, Crustation and Bleeding seen at the Lip

Fig. III- Sloughing seen in lower labial vestibule, Erythematous base covered with peeling of the overlying mucosa with erosions seen

Fig. IV- Erythematous area with sloughing of the overlying mucosa

Fig. V (a)

Fig. V (b)

Fig. V (c) Healing lips, lower labial mucosa including vestibule & buccal mucosa.